

SEM-EBSD

SEM-EBSD analysis was used to characterize the microstructure in terms of grain size and dislocation density in ferrite and austenite, depending on different DED process conditions. The method was employed to evaluate the average grain size of ferrite and austenite, as well as the dislocation density. **Fig. 1_SUPP** presents the grain size distribution of ferrite and austenite. The bar chart clearly illustrates the progressive increase in the fraction of small ferrite grains and, conversely, the coarsening of austenite grains across the SDM800, SDM1600, and SDM2400 samples. Additionally, it is evident that the grain size distribution of ferrite is relatively uniform in terms of area fraction, whereas in austenite, small grains dominate, and the area fraction gradually decreases with increasing grain size in all samples (SDM800, SDM1600, and SDM2400).

Fig. 1_SUPP Grain size distribution in ferrite and austenite of a) SDM800, b) SDM1600, and c) SDM2400 samples.

Similarly, **Fig. 2_SUPP** shows a gradual decrease in dislocation density in both ferrite and austenite phases across the SDM800, SDM1600, and SDM2400 samples.

Fig. 2_SUPP Geometrically Necessary Dislocations (GNDs) distribution in ferrite and austenite of a) SDM800, b) SDM1600, and c) SDM2400 samples.